

INTELLECTUAL CONSPIRACY TO BREAK NATION UNDER THE NAME OF WOMEN LAW

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Abstract

All well-wishers of India must now get united. We may have internal differences, but let us get united for the sake of protecting our culture. When some alien forces are trying to destroy the Hindu saint and the Hindu culture by using some Hindus as stooges, the Hindus won't allow them to destroy Hindu culture. They keep hatching various conspiracies to disturb and disrupt the great civilization. There were four ancient civilization-Romans, Greek, Egyptian and Indian. They have destroyed the civilizations of Rome, Greece and Egypt already; now only that of India is still alive. Give importance to your culture because your post will no more be your after a certain period of time, but this culture has been serving you in a great manner for centuries together.

Therefore today the world does not need bombs, terrorism and exploiters. What the world needs today is Yoga of Indian culture, Self-knowledge and the spirit of –Vasudhaiva Kutumbkam-The whole world is one single family. The world needs peace; and not disturbance and chaos. Therefore, to protect this culture, to stay united is the service to entire mankind. The more the saints had to bear atrocity, the greater is their recognition amidst society. Great men like Aadya Shankaracharyaji, Kabirji, Mahatma Buddha and Vivekanandaji have tolerated persecution.

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Introduction

Conspiracies have been plotted against any saint or great man who worked for the protection of culture and mass awakening. Jagat Guru Adi Shankaracharya was defamed so much that he could not get wood for performing the funeral rites of his mother. Dirty allegations

were leveled against Hindu religious celebrities. Lakhs of foreign funded NGOs are being run in the country and they have kept entire politics of this country virtually under their control. Why saints are defamed so much and jailed? Those who cannot tolerate the works of public awakening and national good carried out by saints plot conspiracies to oppress and jail them in order to defame them. It is but religious duty of Hindus to protect themselves from the Christian conspiracy with all their body, mind and wealth and immediately douse the conflagration of Christianity that is progressively taking into its fold Hindus and indirectly moving fast towards them. Only this way can secularism, religious fraternity and true democracy can be protected, otherwise independence may again be threatened.

Objective-

Making awareness of society to avoid the intellectual conspiracies against Hindu religious celebrities by using women law.

Material and Method:

This paper is Empirical and philosophical. The paper is basically compiled with the help of various secondary sources like books, journals magazines, internet etc.

Discussion:

The way the anti-rape law is used as a weapon is not a good sign for the society. It will create chaos and disorder in the society. **To prevent this disease that is worse than cancer or even AIDS, Supreme Court would need to intervene.** The Anti-rape law has provision that just on the basis of an allegation Leveled by a complainant, anyone can be sent to jail without any evidence. This law is being misused more widely than the anti-dowry law which could be misused to implicate any man at any time simply by the statement given by a girl or a woman. This should be changed soon else innocent eminent persons and ordinary persons will continue becoming victims of its misuse.

Increase in the abuse of this law enacted to protect women for destroying any man's life by leveling false allegations against him, and to destroy the life of many women like his mother, sister, wife etc. has made it a problem for men and women. A false allegation of rape creates havoc in the life of the accused. His family faces isolation as the society expels him without knowing the truth. So many people have committed suicide. Who will give justice to them? It is a massive conspiracy to weaken and destabilize the nation by leveling baseless allegations against eminent persons. If these conspirators succeed in their mission, the country will have to

face a humiliating environment, where neither men nor women will safe. Anti-social elements are trying to disgrace the women of our nation for their selfish gains. It is necessary to review the new anti-rape laws. An amendment is necessary to prevent its misuse. Any law should have least possibility of its misuse. An exercise should be carried out to make laws practical and effective. In spite of this the police too imposed the POCSO ACT on the innocent people.

Ideological subversion is the process which is legitimate and open. It destroys things like race, religion ideology and government system of any country. Then the ideology and government system of the other country is imposed on it. Just as we change the brain of every citizen of the country of our enemy to such an extent that despite the abundance of information, no one is able to come to sensible conclusions in the interest of defending themselves, their community and their country.

It's a great brainwashing process. It is a simple method to make somebody a permanent fool or crazy through brainwashing. It has to be done cleverly in such slow steps that people would hardly realize that they are being slow-poisoned to degenerate. There are four steps to transform the thinking and behavior of an entire population, over generations.

1. Demoralization
2. Destabilization
3. Crisis
4. Normalization.

The young generation is being made spineless and slavish under a well-planned conspiracy of defaming the saints through their character assassination; who are strengthening the morals of Indian youth through inculcation of divine cultural traits. We should uproot and throw the foreign powers out of India immediately.

It is fashionable these days to level charges of harassment and rape. This is the question in many people's minds. New laws were made after the shameful Nirbhaya incident, but have cases of rape decreased? It is debatable but sensationalism over such cases of rape and harassment has increased. In such cases it is very disgusting that on the name of media trial alleged accused has to go through denigration, defamation. In major cases the accused person proved innocent on investigation.

Present View towards Hindu religion and Hindu Culture:

The saint community from all over country have come out in support of Dharendra Krishna Shashtri of Bageshwar Dham, who is mired in controversy over delivering miracles, and said they were prepared to give a befitting reply to whoever tries to play with faith of Hindu society.

Ramanujacharya Vidyacharya Vasudevacharya announced that a 10-page booklet on the subject of prevention of love jihad, rituals of Hindu families is being prepared by sant samaj and the same would be distributed to every household. Speaking on homosexuality, he said a conspiracy is being hatched to destroy the rituals and to play with the culture.

Hindu Jagran Manch organized a conference of youth activists near Premnagar Chhath Ghat on Sunday. The chief speaker of the occasion was Dr Suman Kumar, regional organizational secretary of Hindu Jagran Manch and senior Pracharak of Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh. The chief guest of the event was Sadhvi Ladli Sharan.

Addressing the gathering, Dr Suman (An eminent personality who is Christian Father and Converted into Hindu religion after deep study of BhagavadGita) said the Hindus were becoming victims of a larger conspiracy aimed at making dents in their faith, religion and their very existence. Christian missioneries are converting Hindus in a bid to disintegrate the community ever since Independence..

Dr .Suman hailed the Jharkhand government for bringing anti-conversion Bill to safeguard the Hindus. He said Ayodhya is the holy birthplace of Lord Rama just like other religions have their own holy places. No mosque can be allowed near the temple.

Dr. Suman said Lord Rama is the centre of faith for Indians, but it is unfortunate that a sizeable number of political parties question the very existence of the Hindu God.

From Ancient times Truth & Good is facing such conspiracies from bad and evil forces but history shows Truth has always won. As Hindu Aryans its our right & duty to protect our Dharma & the saints of Sanatana Hindu Dharma...

Dharmo rakshati rakshitah

After Reading about the conspiracy and treatment rendered to a Saint who gave-up his family, wealth, and youth for God and the welfare of humanity in His twenties.

India has been enslaved by paid media empire today that runs on tainted money and foreign run institutions. Their enemy has been the Hindu Saint in India who has 40 million devotees, fights and undoes conversions, restores Hindu Vedic glory with 400 charitable

organizations, 50 Gurukuls and 17000 children's education centres, builds houses for the poor, donates to natural calamities more than the state governments themselves and calls a spade a spade. No wonder Hindu saint has been jailed on conspiracy on charges that were fraudulent on arrival and debunked by witnesses.

The Sanatan Sansta , in its statement pointed out that the Communist parties, which have always taken anti-Hindu stance on all issues, describe themselves as atheists and unrighteous. "They always spew poison only against Hindu Dharma. They are spreading false propaganda against Mataji because her work has been an eye sore for the Communists," said the Sanatan Sansta.

Conclusion –Time for society to get alert has come. It has become necessary for us to understand the conspiracies hatched to destroy the roots of our Dharma and culture. Raise your voice of protest against the laws made for framing innocent persons to break our nation.

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